

Sensitivity of a lumped-capacitance building thermal modelling approach for energy-market-scale flexibility studies

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Julia-based open-source building stock modelling tool - *ArchetypeBuildingModel.jl* (ABM.jl)

Aims of the tool

1. Modelling of flexible building stock HVAC demand
2. Integration with large-scale energy system models

Goals of this paper

1. Demonstrate that ABM.jl compares well against dedicated simulation software
2. Explore the ABM.jl sensitivity to key modelling and parameter assumptions

IDA ESBO & ICE

ABM.jl

Calibration and sensitivity analysis

Results comparison

Conclusions

- ABM.jl performance seems promising for energy-system-scale applications.
- However, caution is advised when dealing with structures heterogeneous in terms of thermal mass

Keywords: building energy modelling; building simulation; lumped-parameter model

Highlights

- Julia-based open-source building stock modelling tool.
- Designed for integration with large-scale energy system models.
- Reality check against dedicated building simulation software.
- Exploration of sensitivities to key parameter and modelling assumptions.

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Abstract

Despite the wealth of literature on building energy management, building-stock-scale models depicting its impact for energy-market-scale optimisation models are lacking. Thus, an open-source tool called *ArchetypeBuildingModel.jl* has been developed specifically for this purpose, aggregating building-stock-level statistical and technical data into desired simplified lumped-capacitance thermal models compatible with existing open-source energy system modelling frameworks. This paper aims to demonstrate the feasibility of such simplified thermal models via comparisons against dedicated building simulation software, as well as examine the sensitivities arising from the key modelling and parameter assumptions. Parameter and modelling assumptions corroborated by existing literature achieved acceptable performance according to ASHRAE Guideline 14 across all tested buildings and nodal configurations, although caution is advised when modelling buildings with structures heterogeneous in terms of thermal mass. Nevertheless, *ArchetypeBuildingModel.jl* performance was found to be robust against uncertain key parameter assumptions, making it plausible for energy-market-scale applications.

1 Introduction

Energy systems across the globe are facing a transition from the traditional dispatchable fossil-fuel-based paradigm towards a zero-carbon-energy future, driven by climate change mitigation and risks related to reliance on imported fossil fuels among other things [1]. In recent decades, the power sector has taken massive leaps towards greener electricity generation, aided by development in variable renewable electricity (VRE) generation technologies [2]. As a result, electrification has become an appealing option for decarbonising much of our economy, stimulating integration of traditionally separate sectors like heating and transportation [3]. Unfortunately, the limited dispatchability of VRE complicates maintaining the balance of generation and the demand [4], emphasising the flexibility potential of demand response (DR) in the electrified sectors [5]. For example, the concept of an *energy-flexible building* has attracted a lot of attention in recent years [6].

In essence, building energy flexibility means the ability of a building to adapt its energy demand profile without compromising its technical limitations or inhabitant comfort [6]. Since inhabitants are rarely aware of nor care about the exact operation of their heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, these loads hold a lot of promise for DR applications [7, 8]. However, current literature has mostly focused on individual buildings, districts, or cities, while studies on the national- or sector-scale are lacking by comparison [8]. In order to study the potential role of building energy flexibility in existing and future energy markets, adaptable building-stock-scale modelling approaches are required [9].

This paper is organised as follows: Section 1.1 summarises the relevant scientific background, while Section 1.2 defines the aims of this paper relative to existing research. Section 2 introduces *ArchetypeBuildingModel.jl* [10], as well as describes the IDA ESBO [11] and IDA ICE [12] building models used for comparison. Sec-

tion 3 explains the simulations, the used computational environment, as well as the key results discussed further in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 draws conclusions and outlines the need for future work.

1.1 Background

In order to understand the flexibility in sectoral demand, the driving factors for said demand are key. For the HVAC sector, these are maintaining comfortable conditions inside the buildings at all times and providing on-demand domestic hot water (DHW). While there are differences in the national preferences for what is considered “comfortable”, the principles persist, allowing for fairly generalised approaches to modelling heating and cooling demands.

Modelling building stock energy demand is an established discipline, as it often cannot be measured directly [13]. Furthermore, since the HVAC sector is a significant energy consumer in many countries [2], modelling at least the yearly or monthly demand has long been required for policy reasons. While top-down approaches can be very powerful for simulating building stock HVAC demand, it can be challenging to ensure they realistically represent its flexibility [13, 14, 15]. Fortunately, there are numerous bottom-up approaches to modelling building stock energy demand based on building physics, inherently capable of accounting for the technical details and dynamics the top-down approaches overlook [13, 14].

A common bottom-up physical approach is to use a set of so-called *representative buildings* from the building stock, model them in detail, and project their results to the building stock scale [13, 15]. Depending on the used models, the building-level HVAC dynamics can be accounted for quite accurately. However, the process of selecting the representative buildings, as well as creating and calibrating the corresponding models, can be quite time consuming. Various data-driven black box approaches have garnered a lot of attention in recent years due to their adapt-

ability, but often require a lot of measurement data and can be ill-suited for studying future scenarios [16].

Capturing the flexibility in building stock HVAC demand on scales large enough to affect generation and transmission capacity expansion planning as well as the operation of the overarching energy markets faces additional challenges. A significant portion of concurrent large-scale energy system models are based on optimisation methods, and thus can be computationally intensive when depicting detailed systems [17, 18]. While some dedicated white-box building simulation software like EnergyPlus [19], IDA ICE [12], TRNSYS [20], etc. could be employed in principle [21], their computational complexity hinders efficient integration with large-scale energy system models [8]. Similarly, data-driven black box approaches are often highly non-linear, posing challenges to their efficient integration to optimisation frameworks [16].

Fortunately, research has shown that simplified lumped-capacitance building thermal models can capture the overall dynamics governing building HVAC demand [21, 22], although their applicability can vary depending on the order of the model [23]. For example, Modelica has several libraries available for both building and district-scale simulations [24, 25, 26, 27] supporting such models. Furthermore, Shamsi et al. have demonstrated a lumped-capacitance model generation approach using commercial buildings with measured or simulated data for calibrating the resulting models [28, 29]. Examples of such models being used for urban- or national-scale analyses include a depiction the Belgian residential building stock [30], the *TEASER* tool demonstrated for 2,897 buildings in Germany [31], an Italian nearly zero energy building stock analysis [32], an analysis of the DR potential of heat pumps in the German building stock [33], as well as the *EURECA* tool by demonstrated for two districts in Padua, Italy [34].

Further simplified approaches enable optimisation-based model-predictive control (MPC), both for individual buildings and larger

portions of the building stock [23]. Recent building-stock-scale energy system optimisation studies include an analysis of the impacts of widespread smart electrical heating in Finland [35], a techno-economic decarbonisation assessment of the German residential building stock [36], and a pan-European multi-flexibility-source load-shifting study focusing on Germany [37].

1.2 Contribution

As discussed in the previous section, representative building modelling approaches have been demonstrated to capture the building-stock-scale heating and cooling flexibility [8, 13, 23]. However, there are three key challenges that remain from an energy-system-modelling point of view:

1. Selecting a set of representative buildings, as well as creating, calibrating, and verifying the building models for different case studies is time consuming.
2. Demonstrating that the selected set of representative buildings adequately depicts the building stock is difficult.
3. Integrating building-stock-scale models into overarching energy system models can be complicated.

In an effort to overcome the above challenges, we have been developing a Julia module called *ArchetypeBuildingModel.jl* (*ABM.jl*) [10], streamlining the representative building modelling approach by generating simplified lumped-capacitance thermal models of *synthetic average archetype building* directly from building stock statistical and technical data. This approach partially circumvents challenge 1, prioritising model adaptability over accuracy compared to approaches like the one demonstrated by Shamsi et al. [29]. Furthermore, since *ABM.jl* has been developed specifically for large-scale energy system modelling frameworks like *Backbone* [38] and *SpineOpt* [39], the output archetype building models are inherently compatible with similar tools, solving challenge 3. This helps

avoid the need for model coupling e.g. via time consuming iteration between building simulation software and large-scale energy system optimisation models.

Challenges 1 and 2 remain unanswered, however. Since the properties of the archetype buildings are calculated directly from building stock data, the resulting models should, in principle, be inherently representative of the underlying building stock. However, hourly measurements of building stock energy consumption for conclusive comparisons do not exist, and comparisons with other models, while helpful, ultimately fail to solve challenge 2. Similarly, as the generated archetype buildings have no tangible counterparts, model performance cannot be verified directly to address challenge 1. Thus, the aim of this paper is to scrutinise *ABM.jl* performance on the archetype building level, with the following main goals:

1. Demonstrate that *ABM.jl* can compare reasonably well against dedicated building simulation software when used to model specific buildings.
2. Examine the sensitivity of *ABM.jl* to key assumptions in the simplified lumped-capacitance thermal modelling.

Goal 1 is important for capturing the heating and cooling flexibility, as unless the thermal dynamics of the archetype buildings are sufficiently well represented, their flexibility likely is neither. Meanwhile, goal 2 helps us understand how robust the model is, which is important when applying the model in its intended scale for energy-market-scale studies, where most input data and assumptions are subject to considerable uncertainty.

Ultimately, *ABM.jl* requires building-stock-scale verification as well for properly addressing challenge 2. However, this is left for future work in order to maintain a clear focus and a manageable scope for this paper.

2 Materials and Methods

Since the flexibility in the building-stock-scale HVAC energy demand is ultimately an aggregate of individual buildings, tools like *ABM.jl* [10] need to be capable of representing their thermal dynamics to a reasonable degree. Consequently, Section 2.1 first aims to provide an overview of *ABM.jl* for the purposes of this paper, leading to Section 2.2 describing the IDA ESBO building models used for analysing its performance. Section 2.3 then describes two IDA ICE building models used for examining the performance of *ABM.jl* when applied outside the scope of the simulations in Section 2.2.

2.1 ArchetypeBuildingModel.jl

ABM.jl [10] uses a streamlined *representative building* approach, generating simplified lumped-capacitance thermal models of *synthetic average archetype buildings* from input building stock statistics and given definitions. Naturally, this adaptability comes at the cost of accuracy. However, for large-scale energy system models, even a crude representation of flexible demand is often better than none at all. Please note that this section only aims to provide an overview of the model for the purposes of this paper, and interested readers are kindly referred to the available online documentation [40] for details about the input building stock data format, weather data processing, archetype building definitions, and used calculations methods.

Essentially, *ABM.jl* is based on building-stock-level data about the total gross floor area (GFA) and number of buildings by location, age, type, and heat source, corresponding technical data about the building structures, as well as data about the fenestration and ventilation properties. This data is then aggregated and processed into lumped-capacitance thermal models by allocating different types of structures into temperature nodes according to user definitions. Heating systems are defined by the user, as building-stock-scale data about existing heating system

properties is often hard to come by, and examining different heating systems is often desirable. Similarly, DHW demand and internal heat gain profiles depend on user definitions. Meanwhile, weather data can either be provided by the user directly, or a *PyPSA/atlite*-based [41] Python sub-module can be used to automatically fetch and aggregate *ERA5* weather data [42] based on geographical information system data, including optional raster data for detailed weighting.

For the purposes of this paper, a set of select IDA ESBO [11] and IDA ICE [12] buildings were replicated as closely as possible using *ABM.jl* in order to analyse its performance. In practise, this meant supplying the known GFAs, structural properties, as well as the fenestration and ventilation properties of the buildings for *ABM.jl*. As the geometry of the buildings in *ABM.jl* is simplified into a rectangular box, the volume, envelope and interior structure surface areas, as well as window areas towards the cardinal directions were matched manually. Similarly, the impact of the simplified geometry on the linear thermal bridges was manually corrected.

Lumped-capacitance thermal models of buildings used for simple heating and cooling demand simulations in literature typically employ between 1–5 temperature nodes, as model simplicity is desirable and including more increases the risk of model overfit [33, 43, 44]. In order to examine the impact of the chosen lumped-capacitance thermal node configurations on *ABM.jl* performance, four different configurations summarised in Table 1 were studied. The simplest FM configuration represents each building using only two temperature nodes, one for the interior air and one for the structural mass. Meanwhile, the 5N configuration uses 4 structural mass nodes in addition to the interior air node, representing the meaningful upper limits of model complexity *ABM.jl* is capable of. A single-node model was not examined, as they have been shown to inadequately capture short-term variations [33, 43, 44] important for depicting building energy flexibility.

Table 1: Summary of the examined lumped-capacitance model nodal configurations. Please refer to the *Archetype building modelling* section of the *ABM.jl online documentation [40]* for a detailed description of the models.

Name and description	Nodes and included structure types
<p>5N: The envelope and internal structures are separated from each other, and further divided into heavy and light based on their thermal mass</p>	<p>Interior air and furniture Heavy envelope mass: heavy exterior walls, base floor Light envelope mass: roof, light exterior walls Heavy internal mass: separating floors, heavy partition walls Light internal mass: light partition walls</p>
<p>EM: The envelope and internal structures are separated into different structural nodes</p>	<p>Interior air and furniture Envelope mass: roof, heavy exterior walls, light exterior walls, base floor Internal mass: separating floors, heavy partition walls, light partition walls</p>
<p>LBM: Envelope and internal structures are divided into two structural nodes based on their thermal mass</p>	<p>Interior air and furniture Heavy fabrics: heavy exterior walls, heavy partition walls, separating floors, base floor Light fabrics: roof, light exterior walls, light partition walls</p>
<p>FM: Building fabrics are separated from the interior air</p>	<p>Interior air and furniture Fabrics: roof, heavy exterior walls, light exterior walls, heavy partition walls, light partition walls, separating floors, base floor</p>

For solving the heating and cooling demand, as well as the HVAC equipment energy consumption, a simple rule-based controller (RBC) was used. Essentially, the hourly temperature dynamics of the lumped-capacitance models were solved using the implicit Euler method with the simple RBC keeping the indoor air temperature within the permitted range. For the detailed formulation of solving the HVAC demand, please refer to the available online documentation [40].

2.2 IDA ESBO building models

For calibrating *ABM.jl*, IDA ESBO version 1.13 [11] was chosen, which is a lightweight version of the more comprehensive IDA ICE [12] building simulation software. This particular version offers a ready-made set of multi-zone example building models illustrated in Figure 1 and described in Table 2, which are unfortunately no longer included in later versions. While rather typical examples of Finnish construction especially around 2010s, these example buildings are not strictly representative of the Finnish building stock in any well-defined manner. Regardless, the example buildings provide us with an interesting set of structures and building geometries to model, summarised in Tables 2 and 3.

The modelled 1-storey detached house uses lightweight wooden framed wall and roof structures with a concrete slab floor. The 2-storey detached house is otherwise similar, but peculiarly, the separating floor is made of concrete instead of a much more typical wooden framed structure. The apartment block, on the other hand, is entirely made out of concrete. For the non-residential buildings, most of the structures are similarly made out of concrete, with the exception of the lightweight framed partition walls.

Due to IDA ESBO being a much more detailed model than the simplified lumped-capacitance models generated by *ABM.jl*, the following details related to modelling the buildings were changed:

Ventilation systems were operated at a constant rate. At the time of writing, *ABM.jl* cannot replicate the different ventilation rate for office hours for the IDA ESBO example non-residential buildings.

Ventilation heat recovery units were disabled. While *ABM.jl* can account for constant ventilation heat recovery, the IDA ESBO example buildings are controlled such that the heat recovery is bypassed when the inlet air temperature would exceed a desired set point. Implementing such controls compatible with large-scale energy system optimisation models is complicated, and would require additional simplifying assumptions.

Ventilation system radiators were disabled. The IDA ESBO example buildings include small radiators for preheating and precooling inlet air, making it more arduous to calculate the total HVAC energy demand unless disabled.

Internal heat gains were neglected. The IDA ESBO example buildings did not have meaningful profiles for their internal heat gains, and instead use a flat GFA-scaling rate. Similarly, the constant temperature rise in the fans of the ventilation system, as well as the constant heat losses from DHW pipes inside the building envelope were disabled.

2.3 IDA ICE building models

In addition to the IDA ESBO [11] example buildings discussed in Section 2.2, two IDA ICE [12] building models illustrated in Figure 2 and described in Tables 4 and 5 were used for further testing the performance of *ABM.jl* [10]. This allowed for examining how the IDA-ESBO-based calibrations hold up when applied outside their original scope.

Table 2: Overall descriptions of the IDA ESBO example buildings used for *ABM.jl* calibration.

Building	Geometry	Zones
One-storey detached house (DH1)	GFA: 135.6 m ² Storeys: 1 Room height: 2.6 m Window-to-wall ratio: 0.20	Houserooms, bathroom.
Two-storey detached house (DH2)	GFA: 145.33 m ² Storeys: 2 Room height: 2.6 m Window-to-wall ratio: 0.15	Lounge + kitchen, bathroom, stairwell, 4 bedroom zones, hallway.
Apartment block (AB)	GFA: 1608.19 m ² Storeys: 4 <i>(counting the basement)</i> Room height: 2.7 m Window-to-wall ratio: 0.26	6 apartment zones, 6 bathroom zones, stairwell, basement, sauna.
Office building (OB)	GFA: 2694.99 m ² Storeys: 2 Room height: 3.42 m Window-to-wall ratio: 0.45	Atrium, 2 open-plan zones, 5 office rooms, conference room.
Service building (SB)	GFA: 9065.5 m ² Storeys: 3 <i>(for offices)</i> Room height: 2.5 m <i>(7.9 m in mall)</i> Window-to-wall ratio: 0.03	Mall, 2 technical spaces, offices, employee area.
Communal building (CB)	GFA: 1858.91 m ² Storeys: 1 Room height: 3.0 m Window-to-wall ratio: 0.23	2 classrooms, IT classroom, hallway, bathrooms, offices.

Table 3: Structure descriptions for the IDA ESBO example buildings used for *ABM.jl* calibration.

Building	Roof	Exterior wall	Base floor	Partition wall	Separating floor
DH1	See DH2.	See DH2.	See DH2.	See DH2.	None
DH2	13 mm plasterboard finish, 482 mm mineral wool insulation, asphalt roll roofing.	13 mm plasterboard finish, 237 mm mineral wool insulation, 20 mm board exterior.	20 mm AAC finish, 200 mm concrete slab, 207 mm expanded polystyrene insulation. ¹	Timber frame, 13 mm plasterboard finish on both sides.	20 mm Autoclaved aerated concrete (AAC) finish, 150 mm concrete slab.
AB	10 mm mortar finish, 150 mm concrete slab, 486 mm mineral wool insulation, asphalt roll roofing.	10 mm mortar finish, two 100 mm concrete slabs sandwiching 252 mm mineral wool insulation.	See DH2.	160 mm concrete slab.	See DH2.
OB	See AB.	See AB.	None ²	See DH2.	See DH2.
SB	See AB.	See AB.	See DH2.	See DH2.	See DH2.
CB	See AB.	See AB. ³	See DH2.	13 mm plasterboard finish, 70 mm mineral wool soundproofing.	None.

¹ IDA ESBO does not model ground-coupled heat losses. Basement and floor slabs are in contact with ambient air instead.

² The office floors are assumed to be on top of exogenous heated space.

³ Partially against exogenous heated space.

Figure 1: The calibrations were performed using the illustrated IDA ESBO v1.13 example buildings, including a 1-storey detached house (DH1), a 2-storey detached house (DH2), and apartment block (AB), an office building (OB), a service building (SB), and a communal building (CB). Note that AB only shows half of the building, as the model is mirrored to reach its full size. Similarly, there are no gaps in the facade of the OB, as the office rooms are repeated to cover them.

Besides being a more up-to-date and detailed model, the IDA ICE buildings were chosen to represent older Finnish construction practises summarised in Table 4. Compared to the IDA ESBO buildings summarised in Table 2, the structures are very similar, except with less thermal insulation. All of the simplifications in the IDA ESBO building models highlighted in Section 2.2 also apply to the IDA ICE building models, with the following key addition:

Ground-coupled heat losses were handled differently. The IDA ICE models reference ISO 13370 [45], while *ABM.jl* uses a simplified hourly model [46].

3 Results

In order to demonstrate the feasibility of *ABM.jl* [10] for capturing the HVAC flexibility, calibrations were performed using a set of IDA ESBO [11] example buildings described in Section 2.2. The main goal of these calibrations was to identify robust values for key parameters governing the dynamics of the generated lumped-

Figure 2: The IDA ICE verification was performed using the illustrated detached house (DH') and apartment block (AB'), representing typical older Finnish construction practices from the 60s and early 70s.

capacitance thermal models, as well as examine their sensitivity to changes in said key parameters. Different nodal configurations summarised in Table 1 were included in the calibrations as well, aiming to examine the sensitivity of the key parameters to the chosen order of the model.

Structural and solar calibrations were divided into categories presented in Sections 3.1 and 3.2 respectively, in order to isolate the phenomena under scrutiny from each other. In principle, internal heat gains would merit separate calibra-

Table 4: Overall descriptions of the IDA ICE buildings used for *ABM.jl* verification.

Building	Geometry	Zones
Old one-storey detached house (DH')	GFA: 136.2 m ² Storeys: 1 Room height: 2.6 m Window-to-wall ratio: 0.16	Sauna, 3 bedrooms, 2 walk-in closets, garage, washroom, toilet, kitchen + living room.
Old apartment block (AB')	GFA: 3405.3 m ² Storeys: 5 (counting the basement) Room height: 2.61 m Window-to-wall ratio: 0.25	48 apartment zones, 20 stairwell zones, 22 miscellaneous zones for storage rooms, saunas, etc. in the basement.

Table 5: Structure descriptions for the IDA ICE buildings used for *ABM.jl* verification.

Building	Roof	Exterior wall	Base floor	Partition wall	Separating floor
DH'	20 mm board finish, 222 mm mineral wool insulation, asphalt roll roofing.	20 mm plasterboard finish, 106 mm mineral wool insulation, 40 mm board exterior.	20 mm AAC finish, 150 mm concrete slab-on-grade, 112 mm expanded polystyrene insulation.	Timber frame, 14 mm plasterboard finish on both sides.	None.
AB'	10 mm mortar finish, 150 mm concrete slab, 82 mm mineral wool insulation, asphalt roll roofing.	10 mm mortar finish, two-100-mm-concrete slab sandwich with 77 mm mineral wool insulation, 10 mm mortar exterior.	20 mm AAC finish, 200 mm concrete slab-on-grade, bottom 82 mm expanded polystyrene insulation.	70 mm concrete slab.	190 mm concrete slab.

¹ Basement walls partially underground, but simplified to ambient-air-connected exterior walls in *ABM.jl*.

tions of their own, but were omitted from this study due to lack of meaningful profiles. Ultimately, these values were tested against two additional IDA ICE [12] building models described in Section 2.3, in order to examine how *ABM.jl* performs outside the previously calibrated comfort zone. The default *Helsinki-Vantaa 2012 reference year* weather data from IDA ESBO v1.13 was used for all performed simulations.

The simulations were performed on a laptop with an *Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1265U CPU @ 1.80 GHz* processor and 16 GB of RAM. The raw data processing was handled using Spine Toolbox [47] with Python v3.9.17, while most of the *ABM.jl* simulations, results processing, and plotting were handled in Julia v.1.9.2. Each full-year simulation with *ABM.jlW* took around 1–2 seconds on average, enabling wide parameter sweeps to examine model sensitivities. All of the source code and raw data used for producing the results for this publication have been documented and made available through Zenodo [48].

3.1 Structural calibrations

The first order of business was to examine the properties of the structures without outside influence like solar heat gains, in order to identify robust parameters to capture the dynamics of the structural thermal mass. As discussed in Section 2, the structural properties of the modelled buildings were replicated in *ABM.jl* [10] whenever possible. However, two key parameters for processing the structural data for *ABM.jl* remain open, and thus needed to be calibrated:

Variation period or *period of the variations* as defined by ISO 13786:2017 [49]. The effective thermal mass of the structures was approximated using the effective thickness method presented in Annex C, only including the heat capacity of the structural layers until the middle of the thermal insulation, and reducing it based on the surface resistance and variation period. Effectively, the larger the variation period, the larger the effective thermal mass of the structures.

Figure 3: When the *interior node depth* is set to zero, the temperature node is located at the interior surface of the structure as shown in case a), while case b) shows the *interior node depth* is set to one, placing the temperature node in the middle of the primary insulation layer. Note that the *interior node depth* does not affect the total thermal resistance through the structure, nor the structural layers used for calculating the effective thermal mass $C_{\text{structure}}$ highlighted in yellow.

Interior node depth determines how deep into the structure the lumped-capacitance temperature node is placed, illustrated in Figure 3, defined as a fraction of the total thermal resistance from the interior surface to the middle of the primary insulation layer. Essentially, the lower the interior node depth, the larger the share of the heat transfer between the structural nodes and the interior air node, as opposed to the heat transfer to the ambient temperatures.

Structural parameter calibrations were performed for the period of variations ranging from $8.64e4$ – $5.73e7$ seconds (≈ 1 – 663 days) with 11 exponential steps, while the interior node depth was sampled between 0–1 with uniform 0.1 intervals. For each parameter combination, build-

ing, and nodal configuration, various model performance indicators of the simulated hourly full-year free GFA-averaged indoor air temperatures of *ABM.jl* [10] compared to IDA ESBO were calculated.

Figure 4 presents a summary of the structural parameter calibration results using root-mean-square error (RMSE) as the main indicator, as it was deemed best suited for free temperature comparisons. Normalised mean bias error (NMBE), coefficient of variation of the RMSE (CVRMSE), and coefficient of determination (R^2) were also calculated and compared against the ASHRAE Guideline 14 [50] hourly criteria. Mean RMSE values across both the modelled buildings as well as nodal configurations were also calculated in order to identify the parameter combinations resulting in the most robust overall performance. Furthermore, the upper half of Figure 6 presents illustrations of the best results for both the best and worst performing building and node configuration pairs, namely the OB with the LBM configuration, and the CB with the FM configuration.

3.2 Solar calibrations

After the calibrations explained in Section 3.1, the structural parameters were fixed to the robust mean values across all buildings and nodal configurations from Figure 4, namely to interior node depth of 0.1 and variation period of 1.16e6 seconds (≈ 13.4 days). Naturally, this does not result in the best possible fit for every building and nodal configuration. Nevertheless, archetype-building-specific calibrations are not always feasible for energy-system-scale simulations, so model performance under less ideal conditions is of key interest.

Similar to the structural calibrations, most of the parameters governing solar heat gains in *ABM.jl* like window area, orientation, and properties could be replicated from the underlying IDA models. However, two key parameters still needed to be determined via calibrations:

External shading coefficient is a simple multiplier for all incoming direct solar irradiation, accounting for the overall effect of the building’s surroundings and any solar shading elements. Effectively, a value of zero removes incoming direct solar irradiation entirely, while a value of one assumes no shading whatsoever.

Solar gain convective fraction is the assumed distribution of the solar heat gains between the interior air node and the structural nodes. Essentially, a value of zero means that all solar heat gains are applied to the structural nodes distributed based on their respective surface areas, while a value of one applies all solar gains solely to the interior air node.

The solar parameter calibrations were performed for every building, nodal configuration, and combination of external shading coefficient and solar gain convective fractions ranging from 0–1 in uniform 0.1 intervals. Similar to the structural parameter calibrations in Section 3.1, performance indicators of the hourly full-year free GFA-averaged indoor air temperatures of *ABM.jl* compared to IDA ESBO were calculated, with the resulting summary presented in Figure 5. Again, mean RMSE values across the modelled buildings and nodal configurations were calculated to identify the most robust parameter combinations. Furthermore, the lower half of Figure 6 presents illustrations of the best results for both the best and worst performing building and node configuration pairs of the solar parameter calibrations, namely the SB with the EM configuration, and the DH1 with the FM configuration.

Figure 4: Free temperature structural parameter calibration summary using RMSE [°C]. The interior node depth and variation period axes are identical across all heat maps, see the bottom-right corner. Mean values over the different buildings and nodal configurations were calculated to find robust parameters.

Figure 5: Free temperature solar parameter calibration summary using RMSE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]. The external shading coefficient and solar gain convective fraction axes are identical across all heat maps, see the bottom-right corner. Mean values over the different buildings and nodal configurations were calculated to find robust parameters.

Figure 6: The best and worst fitting 4-week periods for the best and worst fitting *ABM.jl* building and node-configuration pairs from the IDA ESBO calibrations. The dotted light blue lines indicate the range between the maximum and minimum zone temperatures in the IDA ESBO models. The shown diagnostics include the maximum (Max) and minimum (Min) temperature differences, and the root-mean-square error (RMSE) for each illustrated period.

3.3 IDA ICE comparison

ABM.jl was compared against the two IDA ICE building models described in Section 2.3 using the robust mean structural and solar parameters from the IDA ESBO calibrations. This was done to examine *ABM.jl* [10] performance when imitating its intended use case, where we are forced to make generalised assumptions regarding the properties of the building stock at large.

Parameter sweeps similar to Sections 3.1 and 3.2 were performed and summarised in Figure 7, with the robust mean parameters from the IDA ESBO calibrations highlighted for comparison. Furthermore, Figure 8 presents illustrations of the model performance using both the ideal and the robust mean parameter assumptions.

3.4 Heating and cooling

While Sections 3.1–3.3 focus on analysing the free temperature dynamics of *ABM.jl*, ASHRAE Guideline 14 [50] hourly criteria are primarily intended to be used to evaluate the heating and cooling demand. Thus, additional solar parameter sweeps using the robust ESBO mean structural parameters were performed to compare the hourly net heating and cooling demand from *ABM.jl* against IDA when the buildings were kept at comfortable temperatures. Figure 9 presents a summary of the results using CVRMSE as the main indicator to render them comparable across the different scales of heating required by the buildings.

4 Discussion

With the results presented by Section 3, *ABM.jl* [10] robustness can now be analysed under different modelling and parameter assumptions. The impacts of the assumptions related to the structural parameters are addressed by Section 4.1, while the significance of the solar gain related parameter assumptions is scrutinised in Section 4.2. Finally, the implications of the IDA ICE comparisons are explored in Section 4.3.

4.1 Structural parameters

Looking at Figure 4, it is clear that no single solution for modelling any building with *ABM.jl* [10] exists, with each building and nodal configuration yielding a different best fit. However, besides CB, most tested parameter combinations resulted in acceptable performance according to the ASHRAE Guideline 14 criteria [50].

Variation periods under $3.17e5$ seconds (≈ 3.7 days) in Figure 4 systematically resulted in underestimating the effective thermal mass of the structures, regardless of the modelled building or the used nodal configuration. Conversely, variation periods above $6.07e5$ seconds (≈ 7.0 days) were much more robust in comparison. Even for the non-residential buildings, the heat maps show less impact for overestimating the variation period compared to changes in the interior node depth. Based on these results, the period of variations of 5 days used by Prataiviera et al. [34] seems quite acceptable. However, they use a more detailed method for assessing the effective thermal mass of the modelled structures, potentially explaining the difference.

In general, *ABM.jl* [10] was more sensitive to the interior node depth assumption. For most buildings and nodal configurations, interior node depth yielding the minimum RMSE was between 0.1–0.5 in Figure 4, with the notable exceptions of DH2 and CB. The issues with DH2 can be explained by its rather unconventional construction summarised in Table 2, with a heavy concrete base and separating floors, but otherwise lightweight wooden framed structures. Furthermore, due to the many zones in its IDA ESBO model, the DH2 has a large amount of lightweight partition walls with lots of surface area for transferring heat into the indoor air node. For the EM and FM nodal configurations in particular (*see Table 1*), combining the thermal mass of the floor slabs with the large surface area offered by the lightweight exterior or partition walls significantly overestimated the heat transfer between the indoor air node and the massive floor nodes, unless the interior node depth was increased to compensate.

Figure 8: The best and worst fitting 4-week periods for the ideal and robust ESBO mean parameter combinations for the best performing *ABM.jl* nodal configurations for the IDA ICE buildings. The dotted light blue lines indicate the range between the maximum and minimum zone temperatures in the IDA ICE models. The shown diagnostics include the maximum (Max) and minimum (Min) temperature differences, and the root-mean-square error (RMSE) for each illustrated period.

Figure 9: Solar parameter sweep heating and cooling demand summary using CVRMSE. The external shading coefficient and solar gain convective fraction axes are identical across all heat maps, see the bottom-right corner. The circles indicate the robust overall mean IDA ESBO parameters from Figure 5 for comparison.

DH1, SB, and CB can also be seen to be more sensitive to the interior node depth assumption than DH2, AB, and OB. This likely due to DH1, SB, and CB having comparatively more envelope surface area relative to partition wall and separating floor surface area, as well as the interior node depth assumption affecting heat transfer to envelope structures more than internal ones. The overall poorer performance of CB unfortunately remains somewhat of a mystery. In terms of its construction and geometry, it should not be anything special, and yet it had the worst performance out of all the examined buildings. The most likely culprit is the exogenous heated space adjacent to a significant portion of the exterior walls, but this could not be verified.

Looking at the results for each building in Figure 4 shows that SB, OB, and AB had the best mean performance. This was to be expected of SB and AB, as they have relatively homogeneous structures and simple geometries. However, OB performing as well as it did was a bit of a surprise, considering it has by far the most complicated geometry. Meanwhile, DH1, DH2, and CB performed worse on average. For DH1 and DH2, the main issue was likely the heterogeneous structures, with massive floor slabs contrasted by otherwise lightweight wooden frames, while the conundrum with CB is briefly discussed in the preceding paragraph.

When comparing the mean results for the different nodal configurations (*see Table 1*), the fits in Figure 4 were surprisingly similar, with the best interior node depth between 0.1–0.2 and the best variation period between 1.161e6–2.225e6 seconds (≈ 13 – 26 days) on average. Interestingly, the 3-node LBM configuration yielded the lowest mean RMSE across all buildings, with the 5-node 5N configuration in second place. Furthermore, the 3-node EM configuration and the the 2-node FM configuration performed equally well on average, which was a bit of a surprise. Clearly, the selection of the lumped-capacitance nodes needs to be handled properly, corroborating existing literature [33, 43, 44].

Overall, the hourly performance illustrated in the upper half of Figure 6 is acceptable. At its best, the difference between the simplified model and IDA ESBO was almost negligible, and even at its worst, model performance remained plausible. Nonetheless, it is clear that without reliable comparisons, flexibility estimates from simplified building thermal models need to be interpreted with care.

4.2 Solar parameters

For the solar parameter calibration summary presented in Figure 5, it is important to remember that the structural parameters were fixed to the overall mean values identified in Figure 4, not to the individual best fits for every building and nodal configuration. Regardless, the *ABM.jl* [10] seemed more sensitive to changes in the external shading coefficient compared to the solar gain convective fraction. This was to be expected, as the external shading coefficient impacts the magnitude of the solar gains, and the value of the convective fraction does not matter as much if the magnitude is wrong.

Without sufficient solar gains *ABM.jl* performance fell below acceptable criteria [50] for DH1, DH2, AB, OB, while the solar gain convective fraction had a less grave impact on the fit. The apparent robustness of SB to the solar parameters can be explained by its very low window-to-wall ratio as shown in Table 2, rendering solar heat gains less significant for its dynamics. Unfortunately, the CB model again defied expectations, despite nothing in its construction or geometry that could clearly explain the observed behaviour.

All of the best fits in Figure 5 were achieved with external shading coefficients between 0.6–1.0, which is relatively high compared to values around 0.50–0.75 found in literature [32, 51, 52, 53]. However, this was probably due to the IDA ESBO example building models lacking in solar shading elements, both from the building and from the environment. Eventually, when applying *ABM.jl* [10] on the energy-system-scale,

using the more conservative values from literature can be justified. The external shading coefficient could potentially be used for calibrating the yearly building-stock-scale heating and cooling loads as well, but further discussion on this topic is left up to future work.

The mean solar gain convective fractions across the different buildings and nodal configurations in Figure 5 varied all the way between 0.0–0.7, making it challenging to make any sweeping conclusions. Compared to values found in literature between 0.0–0.1 [51, 53], the range of values for the solar gain convective fraction are suspiciously high. However, in literature, the structural temperature nodes are often located directly at the interior surface, with a comparatively low thermal resistance between the structural node and the interior air node. The 0.1 interior node depth used here places the structural node ever so slightly deeper into the structure, decreasing the impact of incident solar radiation, thus resulting in a higher solar gain convective fraction. Interestingly, it would seem that lighter structures require higher solar gain convective fractions, as evidenced by the DH1, DH2, and OB results.

Similar to the structural parameter results discussed in Section 4.1, the 3-node LBM and the 5-node 5N configurations yielded the best mean fits in Figure 5, with the 3-node EM and 2-node FM configurations suffering from noticeably worse performance. Additionally, the mean results for the buildings follow the same pattern, with SB, OB, and AB having the best performance on average, while DH2, DH1, and CB struggle. As the solar parameter calibrations were built on top of the structural parameter calibrations, this was to be expected to a degree. Furthermore, a lot of the same issues caused by heterogeneous structures for DH1 and DH2 apply to solar heat gains as well. Still, even at its worst, model performance remained at least plausible, as shown in the lower half of Figure 6.

4.3 IDA ICE verification

Looking at the IDA ICE structural parameter sweeps in the upper half of Figure 7, it is clear that the mean parameters from the IDA ESBO calibrations only tentatively agree with the IDA ICE models. In the structural parameter sweeps, all the best fits were achieved with the largest tested variation period, hinting at *ABM.jl* potentially lacking in structural thermal mass. However, this could also be due to the different modelling of ground-coupled heat losses between *ABM.jl* and IDA ICE, making it difficult to draw any definite conclusions. In terms of interior node depth, DH' agreed quite well with the IDA ESBO calibrations, while AB' would prefer maximum heat transfer between the interior air and structural thermal mass.

Similarly, the IDA ICE solar parameter sweeps in the lower half of Figure 7 were off the IDA ESBO mean parameters. Both DH' and AB' required less shading than suggested by the IDA ESBO calibrations, and the ideal values for the solar gain convective fraction were lower on average. However, the lower solar gain convective fraction could be a side-effect of the model compensating for the seemingly lacking structural thermal mass discussed above, potentially caused by the different ground-coupled heat loss methods in the compared models.

Despite the divergence in the ideal parameter values between the IDA ESBO and IDA ICE models in Figure 7, *ABM.jl* performance remained acceptable, further illustrated in Figure 8. For the DH', it is difficult to see the difference between the ideal and IDA ESBO mean parameters without looking at the diagnostics. For the AB', on the other hand, the difference in performance is plainly visible especially in summer, with the IDA ESBO mean parameters significantly overestimating the external shading.

Ultimately, when aiming to depict the heating and cooling flexibility of a building, the heating and cooling demand is of primary interest. Looking at the solar parameter sweep results for the heating and cooling simulations presented in Figure 9, we can see that *ABM.jl* performance

is quite robust, meeting the ASHRAE Guideline 14 [50] criteria for wide ranges of solar parameters. The highlighted robust mean ESBO solar parameters are within acceptable ranges for all modelled buildings and nodal configurations, although just barely for the IDA ICE buildings. This again highlights the importance of realistic external shading coefficient assumptions when applying *ABM.jl* on the building stock scale.

5 Conclusions

The simplified lumped-capacitance thermal models generated using *ABM.jl* [10] compared sufficiently well against accurate building simulation models, namely IDA ESBO [11] and IDA ICE [12]. Overall, *ABM.jl* seems plausible for energy-system-scale applications, as model performance remained within ASHRAE Guideline 14 [50] hourly criteria even when using imperfect assumptions regarding key parameter for the performed IDA ICE comparisons. However, hourly building-stock-scale heating and cooling demand data would be required for conclusive comparisons, which is practically impossible to obtain.

While the dynamics could be deemed acceptable for representing the flexibility in building heating and cooling demand, the heating and cooling demand profiles still left a lot to be desired due to the crude single-zone approximation overlooking the need for zonal heating and cooling occurring in real buildings. This shortcoming could potentially be addressed by separating the indoor air node into two, one with the majority of the internal and solar gains, and one without, similar to the work by Reynders et al. [30].

Caution is advised when dealing with heterogeneous structures with different effective thermal masses, as lumping light and massive structures together can overestimate the heat transfer to and from the massive structures. Thus, 3+ node lumped-capacitance thermal models are recommended for their robustness, although 2-node models could perform equally well with homogeneous structures. Two or three node

models are likely best suited for energy-system-scale applications, as a lot of the structural and geometric details of individual buildings are inevitably lost when aggregating the building stock.

Based on the results, variation periods above 13 days and interior node depths of 0.1–0.2 resulted in acceptable performance across all tested buildings, regardless of the used nodal configuration. However, the identified best values of 0.6–1.0 for the external shading coefficient possibly result in overestimating the solar heat gains when applied on the energy system scale, as the used IDA ESBO and IDA ICE building models had unrealistically few external shading elements. Therefore, using values from literature [32, 51, 52, 53] or further calibrations using building-stock-scale cooling load statistics should be considered. The range of solar heat gain convective fractions yielding the best fits between 0.0–0.8 was too broad to draw definite conclusion from, although values in the range of 0.4–0.6 seemed to work well across all buildings.

Ultimately, multiple distinct avenues for possible future work are presented to us. In order to properly address challenge 2, building-stock-scale demonstrations are required. Furthermore, the applicability of *ABM.jl* within existing large-scale energy system modelling frameworks like *SpineOpt.jl* [39] and *Backbone* [38] could be explored further, e.g. through fully-integrated national- or sector-scale energy system studies, or via building- or district-scale optimal energy management. Lastly, improving the heating and cooling demand profiles by including multiple indoor air nodes in *ABM.jl* could be experimented with.

A Abbreviations

AAC	Autoclaved aerated concrete
<i>ABM.jl</i>	<i>ArchetypeBuildingModel.jl</i>
CVRMSE	Coefficient of variation of the root-mean-square error
DHW	Domestic hot water
DR	Demand response
GFA	Gross floor area
HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning
MPC	Model-predictive control
NMBE	Normalized mean bias error
R ²	Coefficient of determination
RBC	Rule-based controller
RMSE	Root-mean-square error
VRE	Variable renewable energy

B CRedit authorship

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D Competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. Furthermore, the funding agency had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

E Data availability

The source code and raw data used for producing the results for this publication have been bundled up, documented, and made available through the *FlexiB IDA Comparisons Spine Toolbox Project* Zenodo repository [48]. The included source code is licensed under the *MIT license*: <https://mit-license.org/>, while most of the included data is licensed under *Creative Commons Attribution International (CC BY 4.0)*: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

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